

Speculation on the Emergence of Tsallis Entropy from a Uniform Distribution Part 3

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In Part I, we suggested that the Tsallis family of entropies, $\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q)$, with $q=1$ leading to Shannon's entropy, may be obtained (by trial and error so to speak or guessing) for a uniform distribution by suggesting that $1-1/n$ is a measure of uncertainty, where n is the number of outcomes of a die. This may then be generalized as discussed below and also in Part I.

In Part 2, we argued that if one introduces the constraint: $\sum_i i p_i^q$, then i becomes an extensive quantity and is no longer simply a label of the sides of the die. Maximizing Tsallis entropy subject to this constraint yields: $p_i = \{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\}^{1/(1-q)}$ and not the uniform distribution. This is to be expected because the uniform distribution does not have this extra constraint as we show in the note. In the case of $q=1$, one obtains $\exp(-e_i/T)$, the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) result.

Here, we wish to link the MB result and even $\{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\}^{1/(1-q)}$ with a uniform distribution and also associate these ideas with the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ikx)$, in two ways.

Tsallis Entropy from a Uniform Distribution and the Effect of a $\sum_i e_i p_i^q$ Constraint

In Part I, we argued that one may obtain a very simple expression for uncertainty for a uniform distribution by:

$1 - 1/n$ ((1)) where n is the number of sides of a die

$1/n$ is the probability for a specific number to appear in one toss and $1-1/n$, the probability it doesn't. ((1)) may be generalized to two number guesses/two tosses etc: $1 - 1/nn$. Writing this general form in terms of p_i and dividing by $q-1$ the number of tosses, multiplied by -1 , yields:

$\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / \{q-1\}$ ((2)) or Tsallis entropy

For $q=1$, one obtains Shannon's entropy.

In Part II, we argued that if one introduces the a priori constraint: $\sum_i i p_i^q$, then one is giving weight to the possible i values (of n) which contradicts that notion of i simply being a label, as it is in the uniform distribution. One may note that an a priori constraint means that one knows a priori that there is an average i , and so this is an extra piece of information. This extra piece of information is not consistent with the uniform distribution as we now try to show.

As a first example, consider Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ subject to the constraint: $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$. Here we use $f(e_i)$ for p_i . Maximization leads to:

$\sum_i -\ln(f(e_i)) + -1 + b\} df(e_i) = 0$ or $\ln(f(e_i)) = \text{constant}$ so $f(e_i) = \text{constant}$ ((3))

Here b is a Lagrange multiplier.

In other words, the uniform distribution is not linked with any a priori constraint except the notion that probabilities add to 1. Using the more general Tsallis expression with the constraint: $\sum_i p_i = 1$ yields:

$$0 = \sum_i p_i \left\{ b + \frac{1}{(1-q)} [q p_i^{q-1}] \right\} \text{ or } p_i = \text{constant such that:}$$

$$b + \frac{1}{(1-q)} q \text{ constant } q^{-1} = 0 \text{ for all } i \text{ is a solution } ((4))$$

In other words, a uniform distribution only makes use of the a priori constraint that probabilities add to 1. If one introduces a second constraint $\sum_i p_i^q$, this represents a system with more information and that is not compatible with a uniform distribution.

Linking the Constraint $\sum_i p_i^q$ with a Uniform Distribution

We have argued that the constraint $\sum_i p_i^q$ is an extra a priori piece of information and so is not consistent with a uniform distribution. There is, nevertheless, a connection with the uniform distribution which is perhaps most simply seen for the $q=1$ Tsallis case, i.e. for Shannon's entropy/Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

We have argued that the constraint $\sum_i p_i$ suggests that i is an extensive quantity. If one considers interactions between two particles, each with its own i , and assumes that not only is probability, but i (energy in this case) are conserved, then these two conservation are in fact the same information statement, i.e.

$$E_1 + E_2 = E_3 + E_4 \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((5b))$$

Taking \ln of ((5b)) and equating with $-1/T$ multiplied by ((5a)) yields the MB distribution (unnormalized) $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

One may notice that ((5a)) is linked with a uniform distribution because any outcome $e_i + e_j$ such that:

$$E_i + E_j = e_1 + e_2 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{has the same product probability } f(e_i)f(e_j). \text{ This is a uniform distribution statement.}$$

Thus, it is the product $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ which is linked with a uniform distribution and not simply $f(e_i)$.

We argue that this idea may be extended to the more general Tsallis case: ((2)). In a previous note, we argued that a Tsallis distribution (linked with the constraint $\sum_i p_i^q$) is in fact also linked with conservation of energy in two body collisions, i.e.

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((7b))$$

For the Tsallis case: $G(f(e_i)) = \ln_q(f(e_i))$ where $\ln_q(x) = 1/(1-q) \{ x^{1-q} - 1 \}$

In such a case, \exp_q , the inverse of \ln_q such that $\ln_q(\exp_q(f)) = -e/T$ is:

$$\exp_q(e/T) = \{1 - (1-q) e/T\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((8))$$

and Tsallis entropy: $\sum_i p_i^{1-q} \ln_q(p_i)$ ((9))

Thus, $\ln(G(f(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ and so $G(f(e_i))G(f(e_j))$ is again associated with a uniform distribution.

Quantum Mechanics for a Free Particle

We have argued in previous notes that the free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, has the following identical property as the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ result:

$\exp(-e_i/T) \exp(-e_j/T)$ yields the same probability for any $e_i+e_j = e_1+e_2$ ((10a)) and

$\exp(i k_1 x) \exp(i k_2 x)$ yields the same wavefunction for any $k_i + k_j = k_1+k_2$ ((10b))

We further argue that $\exp(i kx)$ is a complex probability such that one has a uniform probability within a length, $1/k = \hbar/p$ where $p = \hbar k$. In this case, one moves in a circle with one revolution representing motion from $x=0$ to $x=\hbar/p$.

As a result, there is again an association with the uniform probability distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in Part I we obtained (by trial and error so to speak) the general Tsallis entropy form (with $q=1$ yielding Shannon's entropy) by examining a uniform distribution. In Part 2, we noted that if one introduces the a priori constraint $\sum_i p_i^{1-q}$, then this is an extra piece of a priori information which leads to a distribution which differs from the uniform probability distribution (if one maximizes entropy subject to this new constraint).

In this note, we argue that even though the constraint $\sum_i p_i^{1-q}$ leads to a p_i which is not a uniform distribution, there is still a connection with the uniform distribution. This may be seen most easily by considering the $q=1$ case for which $p_i = \exp(-e_i/T)$ (unnormalized). This follows not only from maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the a priori constraint $\sum_i p_i$, but from equating: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ with $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. The second statement implies that any $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ such that $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$ represents the same probability. Thus, the product probability is a uniform distribution. Furthermore, we show that $G(f(e_i)) = \ln_q(f(e_i))$, where Tsallis entropy = $\sum_i f(e_i)^{1-q} \ln_q(f(e_i))^{1/(1-q)}$, has the same property, i.e. $G(f(e_i))G(f(e_j))$ for any $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$, yields the same product which is thus associated with a uniform distribution. We also note that the free particle quantum wavefunction has this same property as well.

